

Germination of *M. anisopliae* spores on culture media treated with four fungicides, IIRRI.

Fungicide	Spore germination at 24 h ^a (%)
Benomyl	0 c
Mancozeb	0 c
Thiophanate-methyl	0 c
Mebenil	11 b
Untreated	99 a

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

nation and development. Mebenil was less toxic, allowing 11% germination (see table). Five-day-old cultures of *M. anisopliae* on media treated with fungicide are shown in the figure. Initial tests for direct toxicity of the fungicides to ZLH indicated no effect on the insect. Cages and rice plants used as food should be sprayed with either benomyl, mancozeb, or thiophanate-methyl to increase ZLH survival during mass rearing. □

Growth of green muscardine fungus on media treated with fungicide. Growth is complete on control and partial on mebenil.

Insect pest surveys in Chhatisgarh

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Chhatisgarh is the rice bowl of Madhya Pradesh, with 3.5 million ha under rice cultivation. About 75% is planted to local, tall varieties and 25% is planted to high yielding dwarf varieties such as Phalguna, RPW6-17, Surekha W 13400, Asha R 35-2752, Usha R 35-2750, and Bangoli, all of which are resistant to or tolerant of gall midge (GM). Only 12% of the paddy area has assured irrigation. Annual rainfall is 1,200-1,500 mm and temperature ranges from 11 to 43°C.

Rare rice insect pests at Chhatisgarh, India.

Insect	Abundance (no./hill)	Year
Miridae		
<i>Trigonotylus doddi</i> (Distant)	0-2	1981-82
Lygaeidae		
<i>Cymodema basicornis</i> (Motschulsky)	0-5	1980-82
Curculionidae		
<i>Nanophyes</i> sp. 1	0-5	1980-82
<i>Nanophyes</i> sp. 2	0-2	1981-82
Chrysomelidae		
<i>Cryptocephalus ovulum</i> Suffrian	0-2	1980-83
<i>Cryptocephalus sehestedtii</i> Fabricius	0-2	1980-83
<i>Phyllotreta chotanica</i> Duvivier	5-20	1981-83

In 1980-83, we regularly and intensively surveyed insect pest populations at 10-d intervals in kharif and rabi. In addition to major, commonly observed

rice insects, we found several other insects that caused damage (see table). □

Control of *Metarrhizium anisopliae* in brown planthopper (BPH) rearing

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Metarrhizium anisopliae fungus attacks BPH, green leafhopper (GLH), and zigzag leafhopper in wet season. When infection rate is high, the insect rearing

program for evaluating rice germplasm and breeding lines for hopper resistance is severely disrupted. We evaluated two fungicides for *M. anisopliae* control and their effect on BPH.

To test the effect of fungicides on egg hatching, five gravid females were caged overnight on 30-d-old potted TN1 plants for oviposition. Each plant was

sprayed with 2 ml of a 0.10% spray solution of benomyl, edifenphos, or tap water (control). Nymphs were counted 11 d after oviposition.

The effect of the fungicides on nymphal survival was determined by caging 20 of 2d- and 3d-instar nymphs on 40-d-old potted TN1 plants. At 1, 8, and 15 d after infestation, the

Effect of fungicides on BPH hatching, mortality, and percentage of *M. anisopliae* infection. For each test vertical bars sharing a common letter are not significantly different using Duncan's multiple range test.

insects and plants were sprayed with 2 ml of 0.10% benomyl or edifenphos. Living insects in each cage were recorded 1 d after the last fungicide application.

In the third test, we studied the effect of the fungicides on *M. anisopliae*. Infected BPH adults which were covered with whitish to greenish spores of the fungus were collected in the greenhouse and placed on moist filter paper in a petri dish. Each dish was sprayed with 1 ml of 0.10% benomyl, edifenphos, or water. Twenty-four hours after treatment, the BPH with fungus spores were placed in a flask and thoroughly mixed with 20 cc distilled water containing 0.05% detergent. The spore solutions were sprayed on 20 of 2d- and 3d-instar BPH nymphs caged on 35-d-old potted

plants enclosed with a mylar cage. Each potted plant was sprayed with 2 ml of the solution. Seven days after spraying, the number of live BPH/cage was recorded. Treatments in each of the three tests were replicated four times.

Benomyl had no adverse effect on hatching, but edifenphos reduced hatching 34% below that with water (see figure). Benomyl was safe to BPH nymphs, producing mortality similar to that of water. Edifenphos caused 100% mortality. When nymphs were sprayed with the spore suspension, percentage of fungus-infected BPH was reduced from 33% in the control to 16% in the benomyl treatment. We are now using benomyl to control *M. anisopliae* in the BPH rearing program in wet season. □

Comparative observations of rice insect populations on indica and japonica rices

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We studied insect pest and predator population dynamics on indica and japonica rices in 1976-77 maha at Tismada, Sri Lanka, in pesticide-free fields. Two 10 × 2-m fields were transplanted on the same day, one with H-9 (indica) and one with Koshihikari (japonica). Both varieties are susceptible to brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* and green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*. Koshihikari is moderately resistant to stem borer (SB) *Chilo suppressalis*.

Insects were collected twice weekly until harvest by making 30 sweeps with a 36-cm butterfly net across the 2 fields. In the laboratory, specimens were killed, separated, and counted.

BPH, grasshopper, and *Leptispa pygmaea* populations did not differ. *Sogatella furcifera* was more abundant on the indica at early growth, but populations equalized at later stages. The GLH population was similar at

Comparative population fluctuation of two insect pests (*Nephotettix virescens* and *Leptocoris oratorius*) on two types (indica and japonica) of rice varieties.

early growth, but after heading was 10 times greater on the japonica (see figure). Cicadella spectra population was similar to that of GLH, being five times greater on the japonica after heading. There were few *Recilia dorsalis* on either variety, and slightly more *Thaia subrufa* on the indica at all stages. The *Leptocoris oratorius* population was highest and lasted longest on the japonica because it headed early. The indica had a tenfold larger population of the predator *Ophiomea indica*. □

Crop loss in deepwater rice caused by yellow stem borer (YSB)

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We studied YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* infestation and control in deepwater rice in 1982. In mid-Aug, when there were many moths, we sprayed monocrotophos 250 g ai/ha from a boat. YSB infestation was significantly reduced (see table).